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Leaves of Suffering, Roots of Strength: An Ecofeminist Rewriting of Sita's Story in *The Forest of Enchantment*

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Abstract:

The Forest of Enchantments (2019) by Chitra Banerjee Divakaruni offers a retelling of the Ramayana from the perspective of Sita, one of the most significant female figures in Indian literature. This research paper brings out the examination of Sita's profound and symbolic relationship with nature through the lens of ecofeminism in Divakaruni's narrative. Ecofeminism examines the interlinked oppressions of women and nature under patriarchal systems, serves as a robust framework to reinterpret Sita's character not merely as a passive figure of devotion, but as a woman deeply rooted in ecological consciousness and spiritual autonomy. The title "*Leaves of Suffering, Roots of Strength*" encapsulates the dual aspects of Sita's journey—her visible suffering under patriarchal structures and her inner resilience rooted in ecological consciousness and spiritual autonomy. The narrative situates Sita in continuous dialogue with the forest, Earth, and natural elements, redefining her identity to the environment rather than through male authority. This study highlights how Divakaruni reclaims Sita's voice and agency by aligning her suffering and resilience with the cyclical endurance of nature. Through close textual analysis and engagement with ecofeminist theory, the paper demonstrates that *The Forest of Enchantments*

transforms Sita into a symbol of resistance against both environmental degradation and gender-based subjugation. Ultimately, this research underscores how Divakaruni's retelling offers a nuanced and empowering reinterpretation of an ancient myth through the intertwined narratives of womanhood and nature.

Keywords: Ecofeminism, Forest, Nature, Sita, Ramayana.

Introduction

Ecofeminism is a philosophical and socio-political movement that merges ecological concerns with feminist theory. It emphasises intrinsic connection between the exploitation of nature and the oppression of women, arguing that both stem from patriarchal structures that value domination, control, and hierarchy. "Ecofeminism is a branch of feminism that sees environmentalism, and the relationship between women and the Earth, as foundational to its analysis and practice. Ecofeminist thinkers draw on the concept of gender to analyse the relationships between humans and the natural world." (MacGregor, 286).

Ecofeminists explore the deep-rooted connections between women and nature as represented in cultural practices, religious beliefs, and literary works. The term *ecoféminisme* was first introduced in 1974 by French feminist Françoise d'Eaubonne, who urged women to take the lead in an ecological revolution to protect the planet. Further, this idea expanded by Ynestra King in 1976. Ecofeminism also represents a broader social movement, awakening women to resist the patriarchal structures responsible for environmental degradation. It advocates for green politics—a system based on equality and the absence of domination. The central goal of ecofeminism is to protect both women and the natural world, recognising their interconnectedness and mutual dependence.

Recent contributions by ecofeminist scholars such as Susan Griffin, Ynestra King, Ariel Kay Salleh, and Karen Warren highlight the intrinsic link between ecology and feminism. Karen Warren, in particular, identifies patriarchy as a dominating ideological structure that categorises society into hierarchies of power and weak, thereby justifying the exploitation of both women and nature:

“For Warren, liberation from patriarchy consists in criticising the patriarchal prejudices that lead to the “logic of dominance”, to create an escape from those prejudices, we need an ethics based on “care”. Between the patriarchal prejudices stands out the overestimation of the unilateral reason, non contradictory and dualistic and the devaluation of the emotional scope, empathic, that establishes sensitive ties with the real and in the other hand the false idea that accomplishment is only possible in conquering (in possessing -we can say)” (Sagols, 7-8)

In the Indian context, figures like Medha Patkar, Mahasweta Devi, Arundhati Roy, and Vandana Shiva have emerged as prominent ecofeminists actively engaged in environmental and social activism. Vandana Shiva, in particular, is recognised as a leading voice of ecofeminism in India. She describes ecofeminism as a new terminology for ancient wisdom. Shiva critiques modern science, technology, patriarchy, and colonialism, arguing that these forces can harm both women and the environment. Such exploitation perpetuates the subordination and devaluation of both women and the natural world. In *“Ecofeminism at the Crossroads in India: A Review”*, Manisha Rao says:

“For ecofeminists, therefore, the domination of women and nature is rooted in ideology. In order to overcome this, one needs to reconstruct and reconceptualise the

underlying patriarchal values and structural relations of one's culture and promote equality, non-violence, non-hierarchical forms of organisation to bring about new social forms. According to the ecofeminists, one also needs to realise the interconnectedness of all life processes and hence revere nature and all life forms” (Rao, 126).

The subjugation of women is deeply embedded within societal structures, making it essential to educate patriarchal systems to foster respect for both women and nature, as women are generally regarded as a reflection of the natural world. In ancient Indian culture, the Vedas emphasised the equal significance of all living beings, illustrating a longstanding connection between nature and literature. Indian ecofeminism draws strength from this heritage. The association between women and nature has its roots in the early Hindu philosophy, which conceptualises existence through the union of *Prakriti* (nature) and *Purusha* (spirit). *Prakriti* is closely identified with Mother Earth, embodying creation, nurture, fertility, and motherhood. Consequently, Hindu mythology frequently portrays female figures as synonymous with nature. However, with the rise of industrialisation and capitalism, women's traditional roles in agriculture diminished. The lack of land and property rights further displaced them, pushing women to the margins of society and reinforcing their marginalization under capitalist systems. In *Staying Alive: Women, Ecology, and Survival in India* “...the death of prakriti is simultaneously a beginning of their marginalization, devaluation, displacement, and ultimate dispensability” (Shiva, 40). When ancient texts are reinterpreted through the modern perspective of ecofeminism, it becomes clear that both women and nature have long been subjected to domination and mistreatment. They are often regarded as possessions of men, and any association with another is seen as a loss of purity or

value. This representation reflects a larger pattern in which patriarchy exercises control over women in the same way that capitalism exploits and commodifies nature.

The Forest of Enchantments throws light on the nature-woman partnership. According to Chitra Banerjee, women are the proper protectors and saviours of ecology and so we see Sita as an ecofeminist who is out there to protect, conserve and guard nature. The character of Sita stands out as a nature's child who is born from the earth and evanesces into the earth.

From her very birth, Sita appears to be the forest goddess, a sylvan deity, or a goddess associated with agricultural fertility, land, and good crops, closely reflecting the goddess of Vedic literature named Sita. “Sita has always been associated with vegetation, especially grass.”(Devdutt, 2013) The name Sita, derived from Sanskrit, means ‘furrow’ and also refers to a Hindu goddess of harvest mentioned in the Rigveda. It symbolizes fertility, the earth, and the essence of motherhood, “This is Bhumiya, daughter of the earth. You may call her Maithili, princess of Mithila, or Vaidehi, lady from Videha, or Janaki, she who chose Janaka. I will call her Sita, she who was found in a furrow, she who chose me to be her father.” (Devdutt, 2013)

One fine day, while preparing the land for cultivation, the childless King Janak and Queen Sunaina discovered a radiant golden child lying in a furrow. This miraculous child came to be known as Sita or Janaki. Adopted by the royal couple, she became the beloved princess of Mithila. Though her true origins remained unknown, she was affectionately given various names such as Maithili and Vaidehi, reflecting her ties to the kingdom and her adoptive parents, “The Earth-born wondrous child, the innocence that was pure Grace and Glory, was the darling of all as ‘Janaki’, ‘Maithili’ and ‘Vaidehi” (Iyenger, 279).

Much like her father, Sita was referred to as the 'caretaker of the palace gardens'. Owing to the mysterious circumstances of her birth, many in the palace revered her as an incarnation of the earth goddess. Her deep understanding of medicinal herbs and ability to heal ailments earned her the title of "Goddess" among the people of her kingdom, "I stroked leaves, dug around roots, and breathed prayers. Behind me, I could hear the awed whispers of the gardeners. Amazing; miraculous; look, they are already healing; I tell you, she is the Earth- goddess herself, appeared straight out of the ground just to bless us." (5) Being born from the earth, Sita shares a deep bond with plants, allowing her to instinctively to understand their medicinal properties. Her ability to identify natural remedies for both physical and emotional ailments, especially those affecting women, highlights her nurturing and intuitive power. This connection symbolises feminine wisdom and aligns with ecofeminist ideas, where nature and women are seen as life-giving:

My strange gift with plants was a mystery to me. Perhaps it was because, like them, I was earth-born. Maybe for the same reason, when I touched a plant, I knew its healing properties. I could tell which grasses cured headaches and colds, which seeds fended off infections, which herbs to give women when their monthly blood flowed too long, and which potions healed the shaking sickness or gladdened a long-depressed heart. (7)

Vandana Shiva's perspective on the feminine principle positions women and nature as the fundamental source of life and wealth, and for maintaining and creating process, which is aligned to the epic woman's character of Divakaruni. In *The Forest of Enchantments*, Sita

reflects the nurturing qualities of nature, embodying boundless love and devotion. As a true admirer of nature, she never plucked flowers to fill her basket for religious offerings, regarding it as an act of violence against living beings. Instead, she selects only those blossoms that the priest specifically requests, doing so with care and reverence. Her gentle touch is so nurturing that even withered flowers seem to revive in her palm, reinforcing her divine connection to the earth. Sita is thus envisioned as the goddess of the earth, an earth-born child destined to nurture and bless all around her. Her closeness to nature is reflected not only in her actions but also in her emotional and spiritual needs. Even as a young girl of nine, she seeks solitude, finding solace and companionship in the quiet presence of nature. Her tender-heartedness allows her to empathize with the suffering of the plants around her, further emphasizing her deep ecological sensitivity and the profound harmony she shares with the natural world.

In her work, Divakaruni vividly portrays the youthful and innocent Sita, expressing her deep yearning to explore the forest. However, her desire is obstructed by societal constraints tied to her gender, which limit her freedom and aspirations, “I wanted to visit a forest someday, though I did not think I would ever be granted the opportunity. It was not something that women did. Even my mother, the most intelligent person I knew, would have been baffled if I confessed this desire to her.” (8) This specific moment in the text can be interpreted as Sita challenging societal norms by longing for the wilderness. In doing so, she not only resists the constraints of social hierarchy but also questions the established binaries of the world, as noted by Catherine Diamond (2017), “The range of women’s interactions with the forest obviates any essentialising affinities with nature. They all, however, begin to cut down the vertical hierarchy of dominance and instead, intimate that a better world exists

beyond binaries.” (97) Through Sita's deep yearning for the forest, Divakaruni not only challenges societal boundaries and rigid binaries but also reinforces the Eastern philosophy that emphasises the harmony between humans and nature. Additionally, she reflects the Hindu belief in the concept of Purusha and Prakriti as two distinct yet unified forces.

After marriage, Sita travelled to Ayodhya from her homeland. Sita took pleasure in her trip through the forest. Sita yearned to touch each item in the forest, including dens, bird nests, and valuable medicinal plants, Sita wished to walk barefoot across the grass and enjoy the connection with nature, “But such things were not allowed to princesses, especially those married into the royal family of Ayodha.”(57) Sita's love for nature can find when Sita gets upset to observe the soldiers' callous treatment of the trees:

“The only thing distressing me [Sita] was the callous behaviour of the soldiers. Could he [Ram] order them not to harm the trees? This is their home, and we are visitors,” I added. “We should treat them with courtesy and not cause them needless pain.” Ram's brows drew together in surprise. Clearly, he'd never considered that plants feel pain as we do. Nevertheless, he inclined his head, “You are tender hearted my dear. I cannot fault that. It's right and necessary that women should be so”. I wanted to ask him, wasn't it as important for a king to feel hurt by others as women did? Wasn't he responsible for the animals and birds and trees in his realm, as well as the people? Who would protect them if he did not? (56)

Even during her time in Ayodhya, Sita recreated the essence of the forest by surrounding her balcony with plants and trees. The rustling of their leaves evoked in her the soothing memories of the forest, offering her a sense of closeness to nature amidst the structured life of the palace, “I

filled it with plants and trees that I had loved in Mithila as well as some of Ram’s favourites, for each day I was learning more of what he liked, including a blue lotus that I grew in a stone trough. Everything had blossomed beyond my expectations. Sometimes I sat here alone, listening to the leaves rustle, and imagined I was in a forest.”(75)

In the ninth canto (sarga) of the *Aranyakānda* (the third book of the epic), Sita pleads with Ram to refrain from killing the forest dwellers, as they had done not harm. She reminds him of the ethical way of life in the forest and urges him not harm even the demon inhabitants living there (Vālmīki-1, 570). Sita views the killing of animals or any living creature without provocation as *adharma* (unrighteous act) and sees it as a major sin rooted in desire. She warns against using violence on nature, stressing that disturbing its delicate balance threatens the survival of all life. Her belief that even Rakshasas have the right to live with dignity highlights her profound reverence for all living beings and her dedication to preserving ecological harmony.

Chitra Banerjee portrays the trio’s journey through the forest as an act of intrusion into a space that had long belonged to its native inhabitants. The forest is depicted as a realm they aim to control and assert dominance over. This idea is reinforced through a sage’s explanation to Sita about the Rakshasas, where he notes, “Each tribe is unique. Tarakha belonged to a militant group that believed the forest was theirs-- the last space left to them, since humans have taken over most of the cities—and thus they wanted to drive us out, through death if necessary.” (127-128) In another section of the narrative, we find sage Gautam discussing with Rama and Lakshman the real reason behind their entry to the forest, “.....perhaps that’s why destiny brought you to the forest; Gautam was saying. To get rid of them for good. To wipe out their unholy ways. To spread the light of civilisation. You must

promise me you will try your best to do that.”(135) However, the Rakshasas were the original inhabitants of the forest and rightfully belonged there. It was the human intruders who encroached upon their land, disrupting their homes and families. Throughout history, patriarchal societies have consistently sought to dominate natural spaces to fulfil their material desires, whether by expanding settlements for sages, cultivating land, or hunting, demonstrating a persistent pattern of exploiting the forest and its native dwellers.

While living in exile in Panchavati, Sita fully embraces her role as a “forest dweller,” developing a profound connection with nature that goes beyond simple survival. Her relationship with the wilderness becomes intentional and meaningful, as she finds beauty and purpose in the natural world around her, “I saw brilliant sunsets spreading like a smile across the sky and molten silver moonrises... I was struck with awe” (66). Sita's deep respect for nature reflects the principles of deep ecology, which recognise the intrinsic value of the natural world. Her behaviour in the forest demonstrates a strong ecological awareness and compassion for all forms of life. She tends to plants with care and feels a deep emotional bond with them, “The plants here were particularly attuned to me... when I watered them or loosened the earth around their roots” (66)

Chitra Banerjee significantly highlights that in the absence of Sita, the flowers and herbs on her balcony in Ayodhya wither and darken. The fourteen years of exile experienced by Ram and Sita brought them closer to the natural world. It is during this time that Sita emerges as an ecofeminist figure, devoted to nurturing and safeguarding the environment around her.

The pains of leaving Ayodhya find no mention, as she seems joyfully embraced by the natural world around her. In Panchvati, she cultivates a vegetable garden that thrives under her

nurturing care. This reflects how nature responds to Sita's affection and is foretelling that her biological clock is ticking away as well. Her seeds of fertility seem to be quickly degenerating as symbolized by the withering mature plants. For Sita, nature mirrors her inner self; it becomes an extension of her subconscious, constantly signalling her physical and emotional needs. Nature, therefore, is deeply interwoven with a woman's nurturing spirit, her very existence, and her inner psyche, this is illustrated as, "Women's monthly fertility cycle, the tiring symbiosis of pregnancy, the wrench of child birth and the plea sure of suckling an infant, these things already ground women's consciousness in the knowledge of being coterminous with nature. However tacit or unconscious this identity may be for many women ...it is nevertheless "a fact of life" (Salleh, 340)

In Panchavati, Sita discovers a sanctuary that profoundly nourishes her soul. The forest becomes a symbol of liberation and spiritual fulfilment, resonating with her deep-seated longing for harmony and serenity. She observes, "I knew I'd miss the forest despite its hardships, for I'd known a kind of freedom here, a lightness that I had never experience again" (74). This statement highlights her intimate bond with nature, a space where her intrinsic values of tranquillity and simplicity are reflected in the forest's silent resilience.

During the early days of their exile, Sita's efforts to connect with the forest creatures were met with resistance from Lakshman, who disapproved of her friendship with them. He cautioned her that these beings were shape-shifters and potentially dangerous. Although Sita did not directly oppose his opinion, she quietly continued her affection and respect for the forest and its inhabitants. In the later days of her banishment in the forest, Sita even cultivated a vegetable garden using seeds gifted by Ahalya. Amidst the forest's serenity, Divakaruni's Sita notices a particular kind of change in Ram's personality, "Ram was finally able to relax. For the first time

since I had known him, he could forget about being a righteous ruler". (138). The romantic connection and intimacy between Ram and Sita blossomed only because they were immersed in the embrace of nature. Within the confines of the palace, Ram primarily embodied the righteous heir, focused solely on his responsibilities toward his subject. However, in the forest, away from royal obligations, his affectionate and tender side emerged, allowing their bond as husband and wife to deepen and grow stronger.

Divakaruni redefines the forest not merely as a site of exile or banishment but as one of spiritual awakening and autonomy. The forest, in contrast to the rigid hierarchies of Ayodhya, becomes a sanctuary where Sita reconnects with her inner self and the rhythms of nature. Her connection to the flora and fauna mirrors her nurturing instincts and resilience. The wilderness becomes a mirror for her own wild, untamed inner strength. Unlike traditional retellings, which often portray the forest as a space of punishment or peril, Divakaruni depicts it as a sacred and healing domain. Sita's love for nature is shown in her conversations with trees, her herbal healing practices, and her attunement to the seasons, elements that resonate with indigenous and ecofeminist wisdom.

While held captive in the Ashoka garden, nature seemed to offer solace to Sita during her moments of despair. Like a nurturing mother comforting her child, the natural surroundings embraced her as she wept with her face pressed against the earth. The plants and animals appeared to sense her pain, silently mourning with her and sharing in her sorrow, "...When I touched them I could feel their sympathy for me. If they were willing my touch cured them. And thus we grew to love each other. I was particularly fond of the Asoka tree under which I slept..." (187)

While reading Divakaruni's narrative, scholars observe that after Sita's return from Ravana's captivity, she started dreaming about the events that happened in the forest during their exile. Once she was back in Ayodhya, her heart began to long once more for the wilderness. Following the celebration of Ram's coronation, the palace garden immediately caught her attention. She was quick to notice how it had changed since her earlier time there. Sita not only restored and enhanced the garden's beauty but also created a small forest behind the palace, rekindling her deep connection with nature. Women, as nurturers, are often the first to perceive any harm inflicted upon nature due to their deep-rooted connection with it. Sita's bond with the forest, therefore, can be seen as an intrinsic part of her being, an extension of her identity. In the small forest she created within the palace, she would spend quiet moments in solitude, reflecting on the events of her past. This deep emotional connection to nature stood in contrast to Ram's perspective, who often reminded her that their time in the forest had ended and urged her to embrace their new responsibilities as king and queen.

Ram, under the pretext that Sita longed for the forest, sent her to the ashram of Sage Valmiki while she was pregnant, after learning that the people of Ayodhya doubted her purity. Accused of infidelity, Sita left the palace and entered the forest with her unborn twins. In doing so, she made a conscious decision to value her self-worth and inner peace above the constraints imposed by patriarchy. Sita delivers to her twin sons in the serene surroundings of Valmiki's ashram, embraced by the richness of nature and a community that offers her trust and acceptance. In her times of hardship, she turns to Mother Earth, praying for the well-being of her children. She believes that being raised in nature's nurturing embrace will grant them unique inner strength. Like their mother, the twins inherit her healing presence, shaped by the purity of the natural world around them. Placing unwavering faith in nature, Sita endures the emotional

wounds caused by the man of her life. This episode serves as a reminder that Mother Nature, much like Sita, is relentlessly exploited by patriarchal forces. During this period of suffering, nature continues to offer comfort and care to Sita, who, in turn, fulfils her role by instilling in her sons, Lav and Kush, the values of environmental harmony. She teaches them the significance of living in balance with nature, fostering respect and compassion for all living beings. Raised in the forest's embrace, the twins develop a deep reverence for nature, something that structured and civilised life of the palace would never have been able to nurture in them.

In Samhita Arni's *Sita's Ramayana*, the story begins with a sorrowful image of Sita, who bruised, tearful, and heavily pregnant, walks into the forest alone. The forest inhabitants, noticing her distressed state, ask her identity. In response, Sita begins to narrate her own version of the epic, offering her own voice and perspective on the events that led her there, "I am Sita, the daughter of the Earth, sprung from the same womb that nurtures this forest. I am the princess of Mithila and the last queen of Ayodhya. Let me live here. Sita begged. The world of man has banished me." (8-9).

In the end, when Sita is reunited with Ram at Valmiki's ashram during the Ashwamedha Yagna, she is once again asked to prove her chastity through an *Agni Pariksha*. However, but this time, Sita firmly refuses to undergo the ordeal again. With quiet strength, she asserts her dignity and declares that she will no longer justify herself. This powerful act of defiance marks her final rejection of patriarchal judgment and reclaims her agency, choosing self-respect over societal validation, "Because this is one of the times when a woman must stand up and say, No more!"(357) She acknowledges that she has endured immense suffering and has been unjustly blamed for actions beyond her control. Refusing to tolerate further humiliation, Sita calls upon Mother Earth. In response to her plea, the earth splits open and embraces her, symbolically

reclaiming her daughter. This act marks Sita's final liberation from a world that failed to honour her, as she finds solace and justice in the nurturing arms of nature.

Conclusion

Chitra Banerjee Divakaruni's *The Forest of Enchantments* reimagines the epic tale of *Ramayana* through the voice of Sita, placing her in direct harmony with the natural world and foregrounding her as a symbol of ecological consciousness. Sita's birth from the earth, her affinity with plants and animals, and her intuitive understanding of nature's healing power collectively present her as an embodiment of ecofeminist ideals. Through Sita, Divakaruni challenges patriarchal and anthropocentric systems by highlighting a worldview rooted in compassion, balance, and respect for all living beings. Sita's resistance to violence against nature, her empathy for the forest dwellers, and her spiritual bond with the land underscore the ecofeminist principle that links the oppression of women with the exploitation of nature. Ultimately, *The Forest of Enchantments* not only reclaims Sita's narrative agency but also redefines her as a guardian of ecological and ethical values, making her an influential figure of environmental stewardship in contemporary feminist literature.

Works Cited:

Ami, Samhita, and Moyna Chitrakar. *Sita's Ramayana*. Tara Books, 2011.

Anu, R., and P. Deepa. "An Exploration of Ecofeminism and Myth in Chitra Banerjee Divakaruni's *The Forest of Enchantments*." *International Journal of Current Research/International Education and Research Journal*, Apr. 2023, https://www.researchgate.net/publication/384894015_AN_EXPLORATION_OF_ECOFEMINIS

M_AND_MYTH_IN_CHITRA_BANERJEE_DIVAKARUNI%27S_THE_FOREST_OF_ENCHANTMENTS. Accessed 3 July 2025.

Borah, Rulika. "A Study of Ecofeminism and the Conflict between Civilization and Nature / Men and Woman in *Ramayana* with Reference to Chitra Lekha Banerjee's Novel *The Forest of Enchantments*." *Research Journal of English Language and Literature (RJELAL)*, vol. 8, no. 1, 14 Apr. 2023, <https://doi.org/10.33329/rjelal.8.1.27>. Accessed 3 July 2025.

Diamond, Catherine. "The Range of Women's Interactions with the Forest Obviates Any Essentializing Affinities with Nature. They All, However, Begin to Cut Down the Vertical Hierarchy of Dominance and Instead, Intimate That a Better World Exists Beyond Binaries." *Asian Theatre Journal*, vol. 34, no. 1, 2017, pp. 96–112.

Divakaruni, Chitra Banerjee. *The Forest of Enchantments*. HarperCollins Publishers India, 2019.

Dwivedi, Prabha, Priyanka Tripathi, and Pankaj Verma. "Eco-Ethics or Theoethics? Situating Sītā in and out of the Vedic and the Post-Vedic Societies." *Journal of Dharma*, vol. 48, 2024, pp. 573–592, https://www.researchgate.net/publication/378690407_ECOETHICS_OR_THEOETHICS_Situating_Sita_in_and_out_of_the_Vedic_and_the_Post-Vedic_Societies/citation/download. Accessed 3 July 2025.

Iyengar, K. R. Srinivasa. *Indian Writing in English*. Sterling Publishers, 1985.

Kapoor, Pranjal, Jayatee Bhattacharya, and Sushila Vijaykumar. "Sita in Forest: A Critical Analysis of Ecofeminism in Chitra Banerjee Divakaruni's *The Forest of Enchantments*." *International Journal of Religion*, vol. 5, no. 11, 2024, pp. 8414–8421. *International Journal of Religion*, <https://doi.org/10.61707/zf4g0p94>. Accessed 3 July 2025.

Krishnan, Yamuna. "Vandana Shiva – The Voice of Ecological Sustainability." *Scoutripper*, 25 Apr. 2025, scoutripper.com/blog/vandana-shiva. Accessed 3 July 2025.

MacGregor, Sherilyn. *Beyond Mothering Earth: Ecological Citizenship and the Politics of Care*. UBC Press, 2006.

Pattanaik, Devdutt. *Sita: An Illustrated Retelling of the Ramayana*. Penguin Books, 2013.

Rao, Manisha. "Ecofeminism at the Crossroads in India: A Review." *DEP*, no. 20, 2012, pp. 124–42. University of Venice, www.unive.it/pag/fileadmin/user_upload/dipartimenti/DSLCC/documenti/DEP/numeri/n20/13_20_-Rao_Ecofeminism.pdf.

Sagols, Lizbeth M. "Ecofeminism and Its Ethical Expression in Karen Warren's Philosophy." *Academia.edu*, 2015, pp. 7–8, https://www.academia.edu/es/10850434/Ecofeminism_and_its_ethics_expression_in_Karen_Warren_s_Philosophy.

Salleh, Ariel. *Ecofeminism as Politics: Nature, Marx and the Postmodern*. Zed Books, 1997.

Shiva, Vandana. *Staying Alive: Women, Ecology, and Development*. Zed Books, 1989.

Vālmīki. *Srimad Vālmīki-Ramayana*. Vol. I, Gita Press, 2016.